

D7.3

Topical training and train-the-facilitators session concepts and contents

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GEARING-ROLES project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has the firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness-raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
DG	Directorate-General
GE	Gender Equality
GEAR	Gender Equality in Academia and Research
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
IGOT	Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning
M	Month
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
PGA	Participatory Gender Audit
PPT	Microsoft PowerPoint®
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RAD	Radboud University Nijmegen
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
WP	Work Package
YW	Yellow Window

1. Introduction

This document contains the *Topical training and train-the-facilitators session concepts and contents* (D7.3) and has been compiled by the WP7 leader Yellow Window (YW). It is an output of Task 7.2 - Development and delivery of adequate capacity-building and training activities (M4-M42) and presents the concepts and contents of the in-person train-the-facilitators' trainings delivered at *consortium level*. The training contents are presented in the form of detailed scripts, used by the trainers to deliver the capacity-building activities, and including practical guidance about how to interact with trainees and which supporting material to use.

The decision on which trainings were needed by the partners, and which topics were to be prioritized, was taken jointly by the consortium. This decision was based on the results of the prior self-assessment undertaken by each GEP-implementing partner. This self-assessment was designed to enable each implementing partner to identify at the level of its organization their capabilities in terms of knowledge and skills for carrying out structural change. On the basis of this self-assessment exercise, which aimed at highlighting both available *and* missing capabilities, YW assessed the partners' needs in terms of training and capacity-building, the results of which were reported in the *D7.2 Consolidated training needs assessment*.

As the partners found themselves at the very start of their structural change journey, the main capacity needs that emerged from the needs assessment exercise were basic and similar to the ones that were identified also among other sister-project teams where such capacity assessment was undertaken (i.e. SUPERA and Gender-Smart). Consequently, the following priorities for capacity-building were put forward: first and foremost, the teams felt the need to **strengthen their capacities and confidence to steer change through the use of participatory and co-creation techniques**, as well as to **confront resistances**. The WP7 team could draw on scripts and materials for such training concepts that had been developed for the SUPERA partners, and tailored these to fit the specificities of Gearing-Roles (e.g. Gearing-Roles' partners needed to be equipped for running Participatory Gender Audits while this was not foreseen for SUPERA, and while SUPERA partners had to be initiated about the creation and running of Gender Equality Hubs and FabLabs, Gearing-Roles did not require this as it does not have such structures).

Upon the outbreak of the covid-19 pandemic, working conditions changed dramatically and new needs emerged. To respond to these, a workshop dedicated to **identifying gender-sensitive policy responses for work-life balance post covid-19** was organised.

2. Building a Gender Equality Plan through participatory methods (I) Training for facilitators – Oxford, OBU, 20-21 June 2019

2.1 General concept and target group

This 2-days training was held on 20-21 June 2019 at the premises of Oxford Brookes University (OBU), one of the RPOs in Gearing-Roles. It was organised as the first part of a 3-days training devoted to the uptake and use of participatory techniques to support GEP design, endorsement and early implementation. The second part of this training activity (see section 2 of this report) was delivered in Lisbon in November 2019, at the premises of IGOT, back-to-back to Gearing-Roles first annual conference and a pairing event.

The training focused on participatory techniques, derived from social and service design such as journey maps and personas, which build upon the experience of the participants. It also drew upon the six-steps approach to GEPs presented in the GEAR tool, jointly developed by the European Institute for Gender Equality and DG Research. Step 1 (getting started), 2 (gender analysis) and 3 (GEP design) were covered during this first session. The training alternated modules in plenary and sub-groups, requiring active participation of the trainees.

The audience of this training consisted of core team members of each implementing institution¹, with a view to building a common ground for partners to understand the process of institutional change towards gender equality in research organizations. It also aimed at helping them to identify and mobilize relevant participatory techniques to achieve greater stakeholder involvement and support, to increase creativity and to ensure that the future GEPs adopt a holistic approach to the different issues identified during the gender analysis carried out at each implementing partner.

2.2 Learning objectives

The learning objectives of the first session were the following:

- To provide participants with basic knowledge about gender
- To present the different steps for setting up and implementing a GEP, and to identify the risks associated with GEP design and endorsement
- To provide an overview of participatory co-creation techniques available for GEP design and endorsement and to experiment with these techniques
- To highlight the success factors for institutional change
- To equip the participants for running a Participatory Gender Audit in their institutions

¹ Details about training participants have been provided in the technical report.

2.3 Training script

DAY 1

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
09.00 – 09.55	Introduction and expectations	Brief presentation about the programme for the 2 days Global overview of the project and the link between GEP and work packages.	10 min	Ppt
		Ask each person for a brief presentation (max. 1 min per person) and to share her/his expectations for the training on a card. write on a card what the expectations are for these 2 days. <i>What would I really want to know more about when I leave this training</i> The cards are collected and taped on the flip and in plenary the facilitator goes through them, asking for clarification where needed and pointing out if (or if not) these things will be covered by the program. Facilitator makes brief analysis. Park the list for later.	30 min.	(material: markers, flip paper, tape to stick the cards on the flip paper)
		Warming-up exercise: positioning on a line on the floor as to agree/disagreement with statement “on average women live longer than men because of biological reasons”	15 min	
09.55 – 10.45	Basic concepts on gender	The gender expert/facilitator takes the audience through the basic concepts of what gender is about. The aim here is to get everybody on the same page as to what it means and what the perspective and challenges are with regards to gender. The knowledge the participants have about gender prior to the training is extremely variable (most likely some experts and other absolute beginners) so it is important to get everybody on board with the same vocabulary to describe gender.	50 min.	Material: overhead projector, slides, laptop.
10:45 – 11:00	BREAK		15 min	

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
11.00 – 11.10	Overview of GEP process	Now we start on a step by step procedure to clarify every step the participants will need to take to make a GEP in their institution. This first slide is shown in plenary and each step is quickly explained as well as the general explanation that for the rest of the 2 days we will be taking the audience through each of these steps. Every time when we move to the next step, this slide will be shown again.	10 min.	
11.10 – 12.20	STEP 1: getting started	Plenary explanation in this step. Important is to stress the fact that this working group is going to be the group that is involved in all the steps of GEP and so a long term commitment is needed by its members. This group will meet in different sessions. Sometimes to determine GEP content and at other times to monitor the implementation. Slide 30: This is a sub group exercise where the subgroups (per institution) do a stakeholder mapping for their institution. Distinguish between 3 bodies: 1. Core team: people payed by the project, so the managers of the project. 2. Steering group (key stakeholders in the institution, for example one person per faculty, etc....) 3. Network: Wider group of experts, stakeholders in faculties, etc... that you can activate for co-creation sessions and for the implementation of the GEP. Write stakeholders you want or need to get on board on post its; position them on the mapping. Key points regarding step 1: recap and discussion (10 min)	70 min.	Ppt presentation MATERIAL: 5 posters stakeholder mapping Sticky notes Markers
12.20 – 13.20	Lunch-Break		60 min.	
13.20 – 16.10	GEP step 2 – Gender analysis	Introduction: Listening and observing – principles – link with WP3 and the Participatory Gender Audit (PGA)	20 min	Ppt presentation

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
		Cause diagram - exercise – exercise starts from a persona. In 5 small groups – mix between institutions – issue: getting on a tenure track Explain in plenary what a causal diagram is about and then let them make one in subgroup. The first step of the exercise is to write different layers of causes on sticky notes. When this is done, people are asked in a second step to reflect on which aspects they have the power to do something about in their institution. On the aspects that they can change, they indicate with a green marker (circle it). This second step is important to move the group from analysis into action. It is important that they actually start to believe that they can make a change and this is the first step to do so.	30 min in small groups 20 min plenary	Poster for cause diagram Persona on A4 – handout Sticky notes Markers
		Coffee break	10 min	
		Journey map exercise In 5 small groups – by institution Purpose: to develop a journey map for an external recruitment process for an assistant position. The total journey needs to be mapped. First, the group maps out all the steps and identifies the touchpoints between the candidate and the institution. Touchpoints are put on the chronological line. Second, the group identifies the touchpoints that are most critical for a GE point of view.	35 min in small groups 30 min plenary	Poster for journey map Sticky notes Markers
		Wrap-up on lessons learned – the process of this phase – the techniques available	25 min	
DAY 2				
09.00 – 12.15	GEP step 3 – Design the GEP	Introduction Role of insights coming out of step 2; principle of PGA (task 3.4)	20 min	Ppt presentation
		Overview of techniques for co-creation	15 min	Ppt presentation
		Exercise – personas Develop set of personas dot be used as a tool in the design of the GEP and in co-creation sessions Work in 4 small groups. Mixing institutions. Each group worked for a persona linked to a thematic area of the GEP (except gender in research).	30 min	We provide template, with parts to be filled in; we provide pictures of people.
		Plenary sharing after 1 st persona – sharing of set of 12 personas	30 min	
		Coffee break	15 min	

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
		<p>Exercise: Brainstorm Search for solutions based on the journey map developed on day 1 Groups are NOT mixed (by institution). Identification of touchpoints or step in process, where improvements are possible. Brainstorming using Lotus Blossom. They put the issue in the middle. Search for ideas for improvements.</p>	45 min in small groups	Use of journey maps of day 1 Lotus Blossom posters Sticky notes Markers
		Plenary sharing and round-up	30 min	
12.15 – 13.15	Lunch break		60 min	
13:15 – 13:50	GEP step 3 – design the GEP	<p>It is important that participants understand that there are 2 procedures: one with all the steps to design a GEP and then a procedure in detail for each co-creation session.</p> <p>Exercise 1: Define the procedure for making the GEP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create support – find partners • Collect data • Perform various analyses • Bring it all together (participatory gender audits – PGA) • Develop the GEP • Get it approved <p>Each institution will sit together in sub-group (+ one trainer for those alone in an institution) and to design this procedure.</p>	5 min intro 30 min No sharing	Template - poster to fill in Sticky notes Markers

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
13:50 – 14:40		<p>Exercise 2 – design a PGA</p> <p>Prepare a PGA concept.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectives and scope of the PGA • Participants to recruit • Duration • Guideline for the facilitator • Techniques to be used • Stimulation material to be used <p>They receive a template which they have to fill in.</p> <p>We will ask them in this exercise that they include one new participatory technique that has not been used up till now, and they can explain that technique in plenary. This is an opportunity for facilitators to show and share their experience. The sub-groups should be mixed .</p>	<p>30 min</p> <p>Sharing</p> <p>20 min</p>	<p>Template - poster to fill in</p> <p>Sticky notes</p> <p>Markers</p>
14:40 – 14:50	Short break		10 min	
14:50 – 15:25	Institutional change	<p>Looking at key factors of success in an institutional change context. Practical tips.</p> <p>Followed by open discussion / Q&A</p>	35 min	ppt
15.25 – 16.00	Recapitulation and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tour de table: presentation by each institution on what they plan to do next to put lessons learned in practice • Check on meeting of expectations • Check on confidence and needs for using the techniques • Recap of main messages given (by facilitators) / learned (by participants) <p>Distribute exit questionnaire.</p>	35 min	

Journey maps

Cause diagram

Persona development

Name: **WADJA** WORK-LIFE

Images

Demographic information:

- 34
- A child of 14yrs
- married
- religious and
- parents living
- where she, UK
- experience

Motivations:

- to get a permanent job
- change the world
- has strong values on environmental issues
- family

Description:

- PhD → Emergency
- environmental
- job-doc
- temporary period
- contract
- like music
- she paints
- she write poems

- PROBLEM:
- belonging identity (neighbourhood, society)
 - social isolation at work
 - stereotyping her by her image

Name:

Demographic information:

- 24 years old
- 2nd generation immigrant to Ireland
- Male presenting member of the LGBTQ+ community

Motivations:

- Ambition to lead the research lab wherever he's been working
- Promote LGBTQ+ acceptance in engineering → male dominated
- leader position perhaps access funds
- A leadership position means a pay rise
- Wants a rewarding career but also a good work-life balance for when he starts family

Description:

- Post-doc fellow in structural engineering
- Very empathetic → typically female attribute

Name: **JUMA** HARASSMENT

Images

Demographic information:

25 YO, PhD Student from Mauritania, studies in FR cisgender male, single

Motivations:

Juma's PhD advisor is a well known male full-professor. After conversations with Juma, the professor understands Juma is in a vulnerable position because of his high economic dependence on the PhD position & grant. The professor starts to ask Juma to deliver packages & other stuff to his home. One time Juma is at his place, he pushes/forces himself on Juma. Juma immediately escapes from home.

The student coordinator observes Juma has become sad, isolated & his grades drop. She sees he's not running in the campus anymore. Juma reveals to her in a consultation that he has been sexually harassed but doesn't want to tell who it is and doesn't want to act on it because he's afraid he'd lose his position & grant.

Quotes:

"This is the first time I'm telling about this to someone because it's a taboo for my family & friends."

"I need this grant for my family, they depend on me."

Description:

Juma is the first in his family to have a PhD with a grant. He spends some money for his big family back in Mauritania. He likes running. He has many friends from Mauritania in France & they're all their circle. His friends admire him because of his success at uni. He has strong cultural

3. Building and implementing a GEP through participatory methods (II)

Training for facilitators – Lisbon, IGOT, 29 November 2019

3.1 General concept and target

This one day training was held in Lisbon in November 2019 and was hosted by IGOT. It functioned as a continuation of the two-days session held in Oxford in June 2019. On the one hand, the GEP implementing partners shared their experiences with the implementation of the Participatory Gender Audits. On the other hand, it elaborated on participatory techniques, complementing those mobilized during the first session, such as appreciative inquiry techniques (story telling), the process of strategic framing, primarily aimed at convincing stakeholders and gate keepers to endorse proposed changes. The GEP-implementing partners were also invited to share with the others fruitful experiences they had with alternative participatory and/or co-creation techniques, thus increasing the number of taught techniques. The training largely built upon the experience of the participants, acquired prior to or following the first session. The training alternated modules in plenary and sub-groups, requiring active participation of the trainees.

Some preparation was required from the participants:

- Make a short presentation on the experience with the PGAs, to be shared with other participants before the workshop (template is provided).
- Read all the presentations from the other institutions and prepare questions and comments to share during the workshop.
- Critical review of persona template and of set of personas. Bring personas they have developed and used.

The audience (predominantly) consisted of core team members who had participated in the training in Oxford and who are in charge of facilitating the GEP process in their respective institutions.²

3.2 Learning objectives

- Learn from each other on the experience with PGA and in general to co-create actions within GEPs, and the use of participatory techniques
- Become more confident in the use of co-creation and participatory techniques
- Learn new participatory techniques that can be used for co-creation during GEP implementation
- Be empowered to use strategic framing to obtain management support for the GEP

² Details about training participants have been provided in the technical report.

3.3 Training script

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
09.15 – 09:45	Introduction and expectations	Brief presentation about the programme for the day. Situating the training within the project and the link with previous trainings. Short introduction/review of what we did during the Oxford training	5 min	Ppt
		Ask each person for a brief presentation (max. 1 min per person) and to share her/his expectations for the training, writing it on a card. <i>What would I really want to know more about when I leave this training?</i> The cards are collected and taped on the flip and in plenary the facilitator goes through them, asking for clarification where needed and pointing out if (or if not) these things will be covered by the program. Facilitator makes brief analysis. Park the list for later.	25 min.	(material: markers, flip paper, tape to stick the cards on the flip paper)
09:45 – 11:00	What have we done so far?	Each participating institution is asked to introduce the 3 slides prepared and shared on the PGA experience. Five minutes (max.) presentation followed by maximum 5 min questions and answers. The other participants have prepared questions beforehand. There are 15 min to allow for additional discussion.	75'	6 * ppt of 3 slides
11.00 – 11.15	Coffee Break		15'	

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
11.15 – 12.45	Strategic Framing	<p>Exercises in small group on strategic framing, mixing institutions.</p> <p>1. Exchange per 2 via story telling (appreciative inquiry technique) What kind of arguments do you use towards management & stakeholders to justify work on gender equality? Which problems/blockages have I encountered and which arguments were really convincing? By couple: each tells a story, the other asks questions and reports on arguments used using cards (and vice-versa) (1 card = 1 argument). Then the couples that exchanged pair up with another couple and choose from the 4 stories, 1 story to tell to the others and show all the cards from both pairs. If double cards exist, the doubles can be discarded. Then each sub-group (4 persons) shows the cards plenary with some explanation. The cards are displayed and are clustered (ex: ethical arguments, legal arguments, economic arguments, well-being, etc...)</p>	60'	cards
		<p>2. Strategic framing Short intro on strategic framing (2 slides) In sub-groups of 4 people, we now look at the cards and identify these that have the potential to be used in strategic framing (15'). Results are shared in plenary by putting dots on the arguments selected and explaining orally why they have that potential.</p>	30'	ppt
12.45 – 13.45	Lunch break			

3.4 Visual impressions and outputs from the training

Updates about PGA workshops by partners

PGA workshops

- Target group: Core Group
- Objective: Identification of key problems arising from Assessment Reports
- Duration: 1h30
- Number of participants: 10
- Techniques used: Lotus Blossom
- Main results / outcomes:
 - Leadership: Under-representation of women, lack of awareness about this problem
 - WLB: High degree of feminization and administrative staff-focused
 - Career Progression: Not gendersensitive recruitment or professional development plan for administrative staff
 - Gender Mainstreaming: Very little presence of gender.
 - Communication: Social Networks vs. Reality, Negative impact of events, Resistance to inclusive language
 - Sexual Harassment: Lack of awareness about procedures

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	Target Group	Objectives	Duration	No of Participants	Techniques	Outcomes
PGA 1	Academic and administrative staff from various ranks	Draw insights on the quantitative and qualitative data collected for institutional assessment with a particular focus on the first GEP theme recruitment, retention, career advancement and work-life balance	2 hours	13 (3M+10F)	Causal Diagram with Personas, Lotus Blossom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mentorship program, coaching program, psychological support systems for all staff (and also specifically for women, specific program to support early career women with little children) • Gender sensitive communication guidelines & training • Mandatory gender equality training for all staff and directors • Feedback mechanisms for the expression of employee concerns and needs • Establishing a gender equality unit. • Affordable day care center / subsidies for child care / parental care (for fathers as well), flexible work options (demand-based, not just for women) • Course reduction after maternity leave; performance reviews should not take into consideration the period when women are on maternity leave. • Quotas and positive discrimination for academic and administrative leadership positions • Affirmative action in academic recruitments i.e. shortlisting evaluating to continue until at least one woman candidate is invited for a job talk for each academic position. • Creating awareness among students regarding gender bias in student evaluations (gender bias in student evaluations to be reported and announced by CIAD to students (Center for Individual and Academic Development)
PGA 2	Academic and administrative staff mostly early career + 1 PhD Student	Collaboratively thinking about existing and new mechanisms for preventing and dealing with sexual harassment, sexist and homophobic/transphobic communication, mobbing, bullying and gender based violence.	2 hours	8 (2M+6F)	Lotus Blossom, Journey Map for Institutions of University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential units with responsibility in such cases: deans, directors, CIAD (center for individual and academic development), sexual harassment prevention and support committee, Human Resources, Discipline Committee, LGBT+ student club, SU Gender (Gender studies research center) and Student Resources. Participants were hesitant to distribute responsibilities to a single unit. They were keen on establishing "responsibility sharing" among different units in each case. For instance, they do believe that HR should have a responsibility in setting up such mechanisms at SU, but that it should not be the only stakeholder in such mechanisms. We can identify responsibility sharing as a concrete output. • The problem of "trust" seems to be an important insight drawn from the conversations. The sharing of responsibilities, rotation of committee members, setting up of semi-autonomous/autonomous mechanisms/structures where responsible people are not directly responsible to anyone in the university were discussed. Having diversity in experience level and academic and administrative rank in committee makeup was also suggested. • Given the differences in possible scenarios, the participants did not find a central mechanism to deal with different cases, i.e. sexual harassment, mobbing, discrimination, violence, to be a viable alternative. • A code of conduct / code of ethics outlining clearly the diversity of possible issues that can arise in the university in people's interactions and communications was suggested. Participants were concerned about administrative concerns about university's reputation regarding such cases and they think that publicizing statistics would make a clear statement about zero tolerance. • A guide or other mechanism to make clear what can and cannot be said in written and oral communication was another suggestion. • Platforms for solidarity among SU constituents was also raised as a suggestion. • We saw that many PGA participants as well were less informed or not informed at all about the existing mechanisms at SU so there is clearly a need towards the dissemination of their activities and making them more visible. • Another suggestion was to have mechanism that provide support for subcontracting employees

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- Topic raised -> ongoing discussion
- October 2019 - 1 workshop
- Target group: core group (executive director, head of dep. R&D analysis) + extended group + selected extra participants

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Strategic framing: appreciative inquiry technique

Appreciative inquiry (AI)

AI is based on story-telling:
First 2x2
Then 4x4

Assembling ideas that work

Arguments are clustered. Participants put dots on the arguments they considered the most important (3 each)

Arguments

New participatory and co-creation techniques

Co-creation techniques template

PARTICIPATIVE TECHNIQUE TEMPLATE

Name of the technique: **Gender Wave**

Minimum number of participants: **3**
Maximum number of participants: **6**

Objective of the technique:

- Proactive thinking
- Linking actions with challenges
- Linking actions with responsibilities
- Keeping the actions feasible

Specific context requirements:

- Gather a group for each topic: topic from institutional assessment
- Offer space to move around
- Provide the information about the institutional assessment in advance
- Mixed groups (leaders, researchers, union representatives)

Instructions step by step:

0. Set the context (assessment, previous Participatory Gender Audits)
1. Make groups according to interest/challenge using circles on the ground (the only rules are that there are no empty circles and distribution of participants has to be proportional)
2. Distribute templates, sticky notes and pens to groups
3. Each group has one person who knows the technique
4. Pick three findings related to the challenge (has to be a group decision/ consensus)
5. Identify at least one action for each finding
6. Identify a responsible individual and/or bodies for each action
7. For each action think of the impact. At this stage, consider whether it is feasible, return to step 5 and repeat
8. Present conclusion in plenary (flower shape auditorium)
9. Explain the relevance of the actions chosen

Required materials:

- Template (different colours)
- Sticky notes and markers
- Tables

Advantages:

- Positive thinking-solutions (not problem oriented)
- Stressing feasibility keeps it grounded/practical
- It promotes ownership (turn everyone into actors)
- It promotes communication/negotiation
- Makes resistances visible
- Breaking barriers

Disadvantages:

- Students are not represented
- Not everyone is prepared
- Time-consuming

When to use:

- After the assessment
- In the process of developing the GEP
- To make actions more concrete
- When you have different stakeholders

PARTICIPATIVE TECHNIQUE TEMPLATE

Name of the technique: **Structured Democratic Dialogue**

Minimum number of participants: **5 (best 10)**
Maximum number of participants: **15**

Objective of the technique:

- Establish a democratic dialogue
- Propose and hear out arguments, not only opinions

Specific context requirements:

- Create an engaged group with participants with the best knowledge and awareness to ensure that some actions will be taken
- Be clear about your goals
- Insist on a neutral facilitator
- Pro-gender equality participants should have favourable arguments towards Gender Equality

Instructions step by step:

1. Pose a general question, targeted for specific groups
2. Ask all people to answer the question one by one (an analogy for researchers was: give a catchy title to your article you write in this question). In the second round, ask people to elaborate on what they said in the first round (here is the abstract of your article)
3. One person documents the discussion and hangs it on the wall
4. Answers should be clustered. Clusters are defined by the facilitator and participants put their answers under clusters
5. Participants mark their favourite answers by putting sticky notes on them

Required materials:

- A productive question rather than a dichotomous one
- U-shaped seating
- One facilitator + one person to type (at least, for each group)

Advantages:

- Looks more "science-based"
- Better for more knowledgeable people about the issue
- People must support their stances with arguments

Disadvantages:

- Time-consuming
- Does not conclude with decisions
- Does not conclude with agreements on issues
- Participants need to wait for their turn, which may take a long time

When to use:

- Depending on the question, the best time should be decided

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4. Dealing with resistances – Training for facilitators, 17-18 June 2020

4.1 General concept and target

Individual and organizational resistances necessarily arise when changes are brought to the status quo. They are part of the process of change itself and should be dealt with as such through transformative approaches so as to be turned into opportunities for greater engagement with stakeholders and knowledge transfer. This requires knowledge and skills to be built, consisting in analytical and practical tools to address resistances in one's own institution. Hence, as resistances are a common phenomenon in gender equality projects, upon the request of the GEP implementing partners, this training equipped participants with practical knowledge and skills for dealing with the different types of resistances that may hinder structural changes towards gender equality and integrating gender in research and teaching. The training concept could build on theoretical as well as practical expertise developed, among others, in sister-projects (FESTA, SUPERA, Gender-SMART, GE Academy). Originally planned as a one and half day training to be held in-person, due to the COVID19 pandemic the concept was converted into an online training that was delivered in June 2020, spread over 5 time slots of 90 minutes each.

The group of training participants consisted of the partners' GEP core team members, Gender Equality officers and focal persons as well as other potential agents of organisational change.

Participants were asked to complete the following preparatory activities:

- Complete the conflict management styles questionnaire and note down their result (individual)
- Find an object which represents resistance to gender equality in their institution and have it ready to show (one object per institution)
- Note 3-5 examples of resistances that were experienced in implementing GEPs in their institution and send these to the trainer in advance by e-mail

Training programme overview:

- Session 1: Categorising Resistances (90 minutes)
- Session 2: Reacting to Resistances (90 minutes)
- Session 3: Developing Common Guidelines for Dealing with Resistances (90 minutes)
- Session 4: Resistances Toolkit (90 minutes)
- Session 5: Presentations and Reflections (90 minutes)

4.2 Learning objectives

- To enable participants to explore and reflect on the different forms and categories of resistances
- To make participants more confident with experiencing resistances
- To equip participants with the analytical tools required to deal with resistances
- To support participants to develop practical tools and strategies to address resistances in their own institutions

4.3 Training script

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
9-10.30am	Session 1: Categorising Resistances	<p>Introduction to the GEARING ROLES project and the trainer.</p> <p>Using the Whiteboard facility, participants write their expectations for the training These points are then elaborated in the chat facility Using the Whiteboard facility, participants write their resistances to the training These points are then elaborated in the chat facility</p> <p>Presentation of learning objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enable participants to explore and reflect on the different forms and categories of resistances • To make participants more confident with experiencing resistances • To equip participants with the analytical tools required to deal with resistances • To support participants to develop practical tools and strategies to address resistances in their own institutions 	<p>5 minutes</p> <p>5 minutes</p> <p>5 minutes</p>	<p>PPT</p> <p>Whiteboard</p>
		<p>Presentation of training programme</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Session 1: Categorising Resistances (90 minutes)</i> • <i>Session 2: Reacting to Resistances (90 minutes)</i> • <i>Session 3: Developing Common Guidelines for Dealing with Resistances (90 minutes)</i> • <i>Session 4: Resistances Toolkit (90 minutes)</i> • <i>Session 5: Presentations and Reflections (90 minutes)</i> <p>Present outline of session 1:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHOLE GROUP (40 minutes) • GROUP WORK IN BREAKOUT ROOMS (30 minutes) • WHOLE GROUP (20 minutes) 		

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WHY does this resistance exist? • HOW is this resistance manifested? • WHO is resisting? <p><u>Group feedback</u> The breakout rooms are closed and all participants return to plenary One member of each group shares their discussions with the rest of the participants – the facilitator/host shares the screen with the collaborative Google document produced by each group</p>	30 minutes	Completed Google documents
10.30-11am	Break	The call stays active but participants turn off their cameras and microphones		
11-12.30am	Session 2: Reacting to Resistances	<p>Presentation of outline</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>WHOLE GROUP CALL (30 minutes)</u> • <u>SMALL GROUP PRESENTATION - ROLE PLAY (45 minutes)</u> • <u>WHOLE GROUP CALL (15 minutes)</u> <p><u>Activity: Resistances objects</u> Ask one member of each institution to show their resistances object and answer the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does it represent resistances to gender equality in your institution? • How does it make you feel? • How would you categorise this object based on the criteria discussed in the previous session? <p><i>Methodological note: This exercise uses visual representation to explore resistances to structural change. Some participants are able to express themselves more clearly through visual and physical means than through oral discussions. The exercises offers a reinforcement of the learning from the presentation on categorisation of resistances.</i></p>	30 minutes	Objects are shown using cameras

Time	Programme	Approach	Duration	Observations
		<u>Presentation of Resistances Toolkits</u> One person from each institution presents the Resistances Toolkit (ten minutes per institution) using collaborative Google document as the basis Participants can contribute points, comments and questions using the chat function	75 minutes	
		<u>Closing and evaluation</u> Present previous resistances workshops Provide further resources Share exit questionnaire to be completed during the session Ask for any final reflections to be shared in the chat	15 minutes	Exit questionnaire created using Google Forms

Addendum to the script: Preparatory Questionnaire

What's Your Conflict Management Style?

Instructions: Listed below are 15 sentences. Each strategy provides a possible strategy for dealing with conflict.

Give each a numerical value (**1=Always, 2=Very often, 3=Sometimes, 4=Not very often, 5=Rarely, if ever**)

Don't answer as you think you should, answer as you actually behave.

- ___ a. I argue my case with peers, colleagues, and coworkers to demonstrate the merits of the position I take.
- ___ b. I try to reach compromises through negotiation.
- ___ c. I attempt to meet the expectation of others.
- ___ d. I seek to investigate issues with others in order to find solutions that are mutually acceptable.
- ___ e. I am firm in resolve when it comes to defending my side of the issue.
- ___ f. I try to avoid being singled out, keeping conflict with others to myself.
- ___ g. I uphold my solutions to problems.

- ___ h. I compromise in order to reach solutions.
- ___ i. I trade important information with others so that problems can be solved together.
- ___ j. I avoid discussing my differences with others.
- ___ k. I try to accommodate the wishes of my peers and colleagues.
- ___ l. I seek to bring everyone's concerns out into the open in order to resolve disputes in the best possible way.
- ___ m. I put forward middle positions in effort to break deadlocks.
- ___ n. I accept the recommendations of colleagues, peers, and coworkers.
- ___ o. I avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself.

Scoring: The 15 statements you just read are listed below in five categories. Each category contains the letters of three statements. Record the number you placed next to each statement. Calculate the total under each category.

Style				Total
Competing/Forcing Shark	a. ___	e. ___	g. ___	___
Collaborating Owl	d. ___	i. ___	l. ___	___
Avoiding Turtle	f. ___	j. ___	o. ___	___
Accommodating Teddy Bear	c. ___	k. ___	n. ___	___
Compromising Fox	b. ___	h. ___	m. ___	___

Results My dominant style is _____ (Your lowest score)
 My back-up style is _____ (Your second lowest score)

4.4 Visual impressions of the workshop

Examples of objects representing resistances

5. Work-life balance post COVID-19 – Workshop for facilitators, 7 & 9 October 2020

5.1 General concept and target

Upon the outbreak of the covid-19 pandemic, the consortium partners signalled and confirmed the early warnings that the period starting with the confinement was affecting strongly the work-life balance, particularly of women. At the same time, one of the advantages perceived of this additional burden was that a window of opportunity opened for getting management attention for this subject and that experiences with both problems and possible solutions were gained. A quick survey among the partners to assess the perceived impact of covid-19 confirmed these observations and brought to the surface the need to address issues arising in a gender-sensitive manner. The purpose, as well as the actual effect, of the workshop was therefore to equip the partners with the capacity to steer change towards greater gender equality in a context of covid-19 institutional policy responses. Concretely, the concept of the sessions was designed towards the joint development of potential actions to improve the work-life balance (WLB) situation of men and women post covid-19.

The workshop was set up for the core team members of the GEP-implementing partner organisations. Considering the specific context of the interactive, but online session, ideally two and maximum 3 participants per partner could be accepted.

During the workshop, the group looked with a feminist lens at both the problems and potential solutions. This has been done in two steps, two online workshops of 1.5 hours. The first workshop concentrated on ideation; the second on transforming these ideas into potential actions or measures.

Both workshop sessions relied on the Miro™ platform as shared ‘wall’ where the collaborative tools were made accessible for the use of the participatory techniques. To illustrate what can be produced with Miro, the outputs of the workshop, directly downloaded from the Miro platform, are included in **annex 1**.

5.2 Learning objectives

- Equip the partners with the capacity to steer change towards greater gender equality in a context of covid-19 institutional policy responses
- Introduce the partners to the new reality of setting up and running online participatory and co-creation sessions, using a variety of techniques
- Familiarise the partners with the use of the Miro platform

5.3 Workshop guideline

7 October 2020 - Session 1

1. Warming up – Brainstorm 15 minutes: “more or less affected”

The purpose of this exercise is to identify the type of people who suffer the most from the impact of confinement. Who are the people who experience more or less negative impact from confinement and telework?

Using the Miro platform; poster with a scale: left = less affected; right = more affected. Sticky notes are used and put on the poster. The poster mentions as title for the row: confinement + telework

Facilitator: let participants write sticky-notes straight on the poster. If too many at the same time, ask to wait for a moment. Pay attention to each sticky-note and ask for explanation. Move the sticky-notes based on the explanation received on the timeline.

This first exercise is also used to make participants aware of the possibilities of Miro and to work collaboratively online on a virtual board.

2. Brainstorm Positive / negative effects of confinement and telework – plenary 20 minutes

Brainstorm, poster with two columns. Start with positive, then the negative and come back twice to each column.

What is positive about telework and confinement

What is negative about telework

Example of positive: Save commuting time

Example of negative: Lack of comfortable/ergonomic setting to work at home

Facilitator: let participants write sticky-notes straight on the poster. If too many at the same time, ask to wait for a moment. Pay attention to each sticky-note and ask for explanation. Move the sticky-notes in order to keep the poster orderly.

3. Improving work-life balance and QOL – Lotus Blossom brainstorm 10 + 30 + 20 minutes = 60 minutes

What does the Covid 19 situation and confinement create in terms of problems and improvements to the quality of life?

3.1 Two mini-Lotus blossoms (one for problems; one for improvements) are set up using the positive and negative elements identified in the previous exercise. Eight potential directions of improvements based on positive elements are identified; and eight problems for which we will search for ideas to solve them.

10 minutes maximum.

Facilitator moves the sticky notes from poster from previous exercise to the lotus blossom. Explains the selection and asks for agreement / opinions.

3.2 Split the group in 4 small groups mixing institutions. Let each group work on 4 dimensions to find ideas for things to do/measures to take on these dimensions (2 problems and 2 improvements)

Facilitator splits the problems and improvements: writes sticky notes and puts them in the middle of the mini-lotus (color of central post-it)

30 minutes maximum. The groups work on a poster with 4 mini-lotus.

Results are put in common into one big Lotus blossom.

Each group explains; all the sticky notes are reviewed.

Example of a thread:

Problem: lack of comfortable setting > idea= stimulate to move more e.g. by using podcasts for internal communication (you can listen to it while walking)

End of session 1.

After the session, participants can still add ideas to the two big Lotus blossom posters. The YW team will have integrated all the mini-lotus blossoms into two big posters (problems and improvements).

9 October 2020 - Session 2

1. A review is done in plenary on the overall Lotus Blossom (problems; improvements). **New ideas** are explained by the participant who added it. – 10 minutes

Themes are introduced by the facilitator – 5 minutes

Assignment is given on “how to transform these ideas into “**concrete actions**” leading to more gender equality”. Concrete actions can be at GEP level, institutional (policy) level or even personal level.

Assignment to work on :

- Group 1: IT and cognitive shift – see below for more detailed assignment
- Group 2: Health and lifestyle – see below for more detailed assignment
- Group 3: Time management and efficiency – see below for more detailed assignment

2. Group work – 40 minutes + 30 minutes

Participants are split in groups by cluster. Participants choose in which cluster they want to work.

Facilitator insists on using the sticky notes from the Lotus Blossoms as inspiration.

The most relevant clusters have been copied to be next to the poster on which the group works.

Participants are asked to write straight on the poster, but can use sticky notes if this is easier.

For each of the concrete actions proposed, participants are asked to:

- Define the target group
- Identify benefits (the why) for GE
- Identify risks or (potential) adverse effects for GE

Groups report back in plenary. Other groups can ask questions. –30 minutes (3*10 min)

YW staff as facilitator and as rapporteur.

Group 1:

Transform ideas from the Information Technology and cognitive shift cluster into concrete actions that solve the problems arising and/or leverage on the opportunities. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of gender equality.

Concrete action	Target Group	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality

Concrete action	Target Group	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality

Group 2:

Transform ideas from the health, lifestyle and way of work impacts into concrete actions to improve health permanently after the pandemic ends. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of gender equality.

Concrete action	Target Group	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality

Group 3:

Transform ideas from the clusters on time-management both at personal and professional levels into concrete actions that will improve our work-life balance permanently after the pandemic ends. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of gender equality.

Concrete action	Target Group	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality

6. Short, topical, online training and capacity-building sessions

In addition to the above-presented training sessions, also shorter online sessions have been provided to respond to needs that partners felt themselves confronted with in the course of their GEP design and early implementation processes.

6.1 Operationalising objectives, setting indicators

Upon the partners' request, a topical, online support and capacity-building session was organised for all partners on 27 March 2020, addressing the challenge of setting indicators. The session consisted of a theoretical introduction to a typology of indicators, followed by a presentation of different sets of indicators, among which SMART and SPICED and approaches to monitoring progress. A questions-and-answers session concluded the webinar. Slides from this webinar are included below.

**Online support session
SMART and SPICED Indicators**

Date: March 27th

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement no. 824536

14/12/2020

Indicators...

- ✓ Help you to know whether your work is making a difference.
- ✓ Describe changes or events related to the intervention
- ✓ Provide the evidence that something has happened
- ✓ Require to be clear on what you want to measure

Typology

- ☐ **Outputs indicators:** Indicators that help you to monitor whether you are doing what you planned (outputs). For example, number of capacity building training organised, number of participants, etc. However, they do not give you an idea of the effects brought about by these outputs.
- ☐ **Outcome Indicators:** Are indicators that measure project outcomes. Outcomes are medium impacts of a project. For example, number of participants to a capacity building training seminar that are applying their new knowledge

Source: <http://mnestudies.com/monitoring/what-indicatorsand-types-indicators>

Typology

- ☐ **Impact Indicators:** Are indicators that measure the long term impacts of a project, also known as the project impact. For example, the increase proportion of women in decision-making posts.
- ☐ **Process indicators:** are those indicators that are used to measure project processes or activities. For example, the number of people appointed in different department as a gender focal point.

Source: <http://mnestudies.com/monitoring/what-indicatorsand-types-indicators>

Properties

Properties

CREAM (when developing indicators)	SPICED (when using indicators)
Clear: indicators should be precise	Participatory: indicators should be developed and used together with end beneficiaries (citizens)
Relevant: appropriate to the subject and evaluation	Interpreted and communicable: indicators need to be explained or interpreted to different stakeholders
Economic: can be obtained at a reasonable cost	Cross-checked and compared: to increase the validity of indicators
Adequate: the ability to provide sufficient information on performance	Empowering: the process should allow stakeholders to reflect critically on their changing situation
Monitorable: easily monitored, and amenable to independent validation	Disaggregated: indicators enable break downs for different groups, such as gender, income, etc/

Tools to measure progress

- ❑ Quantitative data: numbers and quantities
- ❑ Qualitative data: provides insights and understanding
- ✓ Use participatory methods
- ✓ Choice of indicators: nice to know/need to know (focus)
- ✓ Use indicators that are relatively easy to collect

Thanks!

6.2 Integrating gender into teaching and curricula

On 2 April 2020, an online webinar with an external speaker was organised for all GEP implementing partners' core teams on the inclusion of gender into teaching and curricula. The webinar aimed at inspiring partners on how to address this issue in their respective GEPs by means of a good practice example. The case presented was from the Polytechnic University of Catalunya (UPC), partner in the GEECCO project. At UPC, a pilot project had been set up in which lecturers voluntarily enrolled with the goal of working towards gender-sensitive curricula and teaching practices. The project leader of this activity at UPC, Elisabet Mas de les Valls, acted as speaker in this webinar. The experiences and lessons learnt at UPC were shared, followed by an exchange between the audience and the speaker. A selection of key slides presented by the speaker are included below.

UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA BARCELONATECH

Pilot programme: Gender Dimension in Teaching project

Elisabet Mas de les Valls
elisabet.masdelesvalls@upc.edu

2nd April 2020

NEEDS – UPC ROADMAP

Gid – THE CALL

- 8 teams – 8 different UPC degrees
- 41 volunteer teaching staff
- 40% men

Teams:

- Bachelor’s degree in Architecture Studies
- Bachelor’s degree in Civil Engineering
- Bachelor’s degree in ICT Systems Engineering
- Bachelor’s degree in Naval Systems and Technology Engineering
- Bachelor’s degree in Aerospace Systems Engineering
- Master’s degree in Applied Telecommunications and Eng. Management
- Master’s degree in Industrial Engineering
- Master’s degree in Environmental Pathways for Sustainable Energy Systems

GiD - FUNDAMENTALS

The 4 pillars for teaching with a gender perspective:

GiD - WORKPLAN

RESULTS – KNOW HOW

ANNEXES

Annex 1. Outputs of the workshop on Work-Life Balance post Covid-19

WHO IS MOST AFFECTED ?

1

" Who are the people who experience more or less negative impact from confinement and telework? "

- DEUSTO
- IGOT
- OBU
- RAD
- SU
- UL
- YW

POSITIVE / NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF CONFINEMENT + TELEWORK ON GENDER EQUALITY

2

" What is positive about telework and confinement? "

" What is negative about telework and confinement? "

POSITIVE EFFECTS

NEGATIVE EFFECTS

IMPROVING WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND QOL

3

" What does the Covid-19 situation and confinement create in terms of problems and improvements to the quality of life? "

DIMENSION 01: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 03: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 02: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 04: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 01: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 03: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 02: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 04: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 01: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 03: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 02: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 04: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 01: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 03: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

DIMENSION 02: PROBLEMS

PROBLEMS

DIMENSION 04: IMPROVEMENTS

IMPROVEMENTS

PROBLEMS

De-stigmatize mental health issues	Strengthening networks of support	Coffee break while having an online meeting			Institutions paying for high-speed internet	Doublethink before scheduling meeting	Create and respect a daily plan with resting breaks	defining work hours strictly
Talks on the impact on mental health	impact on mental health	Prioritizing		IT problems	Ask for trainings to solve some issues	Re-think the goals of our work	increased workload	not sending mails & messages outside the workhours
Online/hosting support from universities	Creating support groups. E.g. mothers with kids of similar age	Psychologic support provided by institutions	Trainings on how to use some online platforms	Pin board and extra materials in case of emergency	Emergency plan to discuss with institutions	having a person within the team to organize whole work and ensure no one feels lost	prioritizing the works you do as a team so that it doesn't feel overwhelming	having a document where everyone has to write down their tasks and how to do them
Online yoga sessions to promote team-building and health benefits	Different meetings for different purposes	Promote other team-building activities	impact on mental health	IT problems	increased workload	having access to physical activities organized through apps for the team	having at least short breaks in between meetings to get up and move a bit	Ask institutions to invest in bigger screens and comfortable home-office furniture
Need for informal conversations	less inspiration / sharing with colleagues	Find alternative ways for emotional support	less inspiration / sharing with colleagues	Problems	ergonomy of working from home	when organizing meetings thinking of incorporating small physical exercises	ergonomy of working from home	Ask for special screens protectors and/or screen lenses
Need to celebrate (birthdays, birth, grants)			cognitive change in way of working	less social contact	less healthy - not moving enough	Guidelines about eyes health and occupational health	Consider working at home for occupational health purposes	sponsor the purchase of an office chair
Focus on a selection of tools	Taking time to get adapted	Coordination of tools	controlled on-campus meetings	Regular walking meetings	online social events	Regular walking meetings	organisation offers online exercise/meditation classes	
Link tools to a specific task	cognitive change in way of working	transitional rituals when changing between roles		less social contact	standard check-ins at every meeting	get a weekly plan	less healthy - not moving enough	develop an information guide for online sources of food/drink/tea, ideas to be shared among colleagues
Specific training on platforms (technical, pedagogical)...	Incentives from top management to take breaks	Training on focus techniques, such as "Pomodoro"	create caring activities/breaks to have tea, to listen to your favourite song, etc.		More participatory online work, fewer passive webinars			Communication through podcasts that can be listened to while walking
								Vouchers for buying vegetables/healthy food

PROBLEMS

IMPROVEMENTS

Policies for taking breaks (eg. no meetings in lunch time)	Need of boundaries coming from management	Defining boundaries with colleagues	flexibility of working hours	having fixed & consistent office hours within a week to work on common tasks	Promote one hour of "self-care"	Rethink publications expectations (DOIx)	shorter working days/weeks	establish clear hours of online availability
Revision and reflection of previous structures	balance professional & personal life	Putting personal boundaries (time-management)	having the option to work from home some days in the week	no time spent commuting	serving free dinners for staff to take home	reminders for real breaks	time management during work	Training on techniques, e.g. Pomodoro
Financial support for some "hard" expenses: food	Avoid pressure on people without children	Understanding other people's situation	The environment: impact of not using cars should be disseminated	We do not need the presence of all people all the time	Opportunity to use that hour for other activity	more transparent workload division	Academic career coaching for researchers on time-management	Avoid "too many" meetings
Linking different organizational units (when doing training)	Improving cooperation opportunities	More possibilities to cooperate with people from other countries	balance professional & personal life	no time spent commuting	time management during work	Easily reaching people far away	Cost saving	Easily reaching large groups
Informal conversations with more people than ever	expanding network	Acces to expertise	expanding network	improvements	IT opportunities	Linking different organizational units	IT opportunities	We could keep on working!
		Plan online international gatherings	time efficiency	larger participation	healthier lifestyle choices	People lost the fear to "online"	increasing IT capabilities	Easy to organize meetings
Dvp new sustainable travel policy	Create email policy	Reduce all meeting times	keep online streaming of events after the pandemic	going to work with new digital technologies, prepared to classes & meetings after the pandemic as well	Reduced fees for some courses	plan exercise times	vouchers for veg/fruit/juice basket weekly	online yoga/meditation exercises
spatial separation of work and home corners in the home	time efficiency	Enforce 'do not disturb' mode/hours	having the option to skip university classes online after the pandemic as well	larger participation	Free webinars	walking activities around the campus	healthier lifestyle choices	Enforce no work after hours e.g. switch off email servers
Slow scholarship	shorter working days/weeks	defragment working time	keeping some of the meetings online especially in big class		Well known scholars speaking in free webinars/ events: E.g. Angela Davis, Judith Butler	clear time boundaries with partners	Holistic approach to health (physical and mental)	structured working patterns

IMPROVEMENTS

LOTUS BLOSSOMS - REVIEW

1

" Review of the Lotus Blossoms (Problems & Improvements) of previous session + added comments. "

PROBLEMS

De-stigmatize mental health issues	Strengthening networks of support	Coffee break while having an online meeting		Institutions paying for high-speed internet	Double think before scheduling another meeting	Create and respect a daily plan with resting/breaks	defining work hours strictly
Talks on the impact on mental health	impact on mental health	Prioritizing	IT problems	Ask for trainings to solve some issues	Re-think the goals of our work	increased workload	not sending mails & messages outside the work hours
Online/home support from universities	Creating support groups. E.g. mothers with kids of similar age	Psychologic support provided by institutions	Trainings on how to use some online platforms	Pin-board and extra materials in case of emergency	Emergency plan to discuss with institutions	having a person within the team to organize online work and ensure no one feels lost	prioritizing the works you do as a team so that it doesn't feel overwhelming
Online yoga sessions to promote team building and health benefits	Different meetings for different purposes	Promote other team-building activities	impact on mental health	IT problems	increased workload	having access to physical activities organized through zoom for the team	having a timer about breaks in-between meetings to get up and move a bit
Need for informal conversations	less inspiration / sharing with colleagues	Find alternative ways for emotional support	less inspiration / sharing with colleagues	Problems	ergonomiy of working from home	when organizing meetings thinking of incorporating small physical exercises	ergonomiy of working from home
Need to celebrate (birthdays, birth, grants)			cognitive change in way of working	less social contact	less healthy - not moving enough	Guidelines about early health and occupational health	Consider working options for occupational medicine/health purposes
Focus on a selection of tools	Taking time to get adapted	Coordination of tools	controlled on-campus meetings	Regular walking meetings	online social events	Regular walking meetings	organisation offers online exercise/meditation classes
Link tools to a specific task	cognitive change in way of working	transitional rituals when changing between roles		less social contact	standard check-ins at every meeting	get a weekly plan	less healthy - not moving enough
Specific training on platforms (technical, pedagogical)...	Incentives from top management to take breaks	Training on focus techniques, such as "Pomodoro"	create caring activities/breaks to have time to listen to your favourite song, etc.	More participatory online work, fewer passive webinars		Communication through podcasts (that can be listened to while walking)	Vouchers for buying vegetables/healthy food

PROBLEMS

IMPROVEMENTS

Policies for taking breaks (e.g. no meetings in lunch time)	Need of boundaries coming from management	Defining boundaries with colleagues	flexibility of working hours	having fixed & common office hours within a week to work on common tasks	Promote one hour of "self-care"	Rethink publications expectations (DORA)	shorter working days/weeks	establish clear hours of online availability
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Financial support for some "new" expenses: food	Avoid pressure on people without children	Understanding other people's situation	The environmental impact of not using cars should be disseminated	We do not meet the presence of all people all the time	Opportunity to use that hour for other activity	more transparent workload division	Academic career coaching for researchers on time-management	Avoid "too many meetings"
Linking different organizational units (when doing training)	Improving cooperation opportunities	More possibilities to cooperate with people from other countries	balance professional & personal life	no time spent commuting	time management during work	Easily reaching people far away	Cost saving	Easily reaching large groups
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Dvp new sustainable travel policy	Create email policy	Reduce all meeting times	keep online (streaming of events after the pandemic)	getting better with the digital technologies to integrate to courses & meetings after the pandemic as well	Reduced fees for some courses	plan exercise times	vouchers for veg/fruit/ice basket weekly	(online) yoga/meditation exercises
spatial separation of work and home corners in the home	time efficiency	Enforce 'do not disturb' mode/hours	having the option to see emergency closer online after the pandemic as well	larger participation	Free webinars	walking activities around the campus	healthier lifestyle choices	Enforce no work after hours, e.g. switch off email servers
Slow scholarship	shorter working days/weeks	defragment working time	keeping some of the meetings online especially in big cities		Well-known scholars speaking in free webinars events. E.g. Angela Davis, Justin Barber	clear time boundaries with partners	Holistic approach to health (physical and mental)	structured working patterns

IMPROVEMENTS

GROUP 01 - IT & COGNITIVE SHIFT

2.1 " Transform ideas from the IT and cognitive shift cluster into concrete actions that solve the problems arising and/or leverage on the opportunities. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of GE. "

IT & COGNITIVE SHIFT CLUSTER

Concrete actions	Target groups	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality
Making more specific training for different members of staff and ages	Teaching / Researchers / administrative staff Students Levels based on IT proficiency Should be disability inclusive	IT trainers should be gender balanced Time tables, taking into account the laboral reductions to worklife balance	
Training and help desk. Specific personnel allocated in the institution to help with IT issues. Personal assistance / personal training Hiring more people in these teams /creating specific team for this.	Teaching / Researchers / administrative staff Students, participants to the public events organized and external collaborators. The idea was expressed to share good practice between universities, to network between the universities	Help desk should be gender balanced Should be disability inclusive	
Allocating budget to increasing the speed of the Internet. Asking donors/ university administration to allocate the previous travel budgets to internet access			If we do not have higher speed at home, women are not prioritised when using the internet. Who makes the compromise? the women!
Using audio-based tools like Discord rather than video-based tools like Zoom for the meetings so that parents are more comfortable working and taking care of children at the same time		Work-life balance for parents	
We should choose which tools we will use. Did we ask the people? Prioritize and choose specific tools (packages of tools) so that not everyone chooses by him/herself	Standarization and prioritization of tools. Listen to teachers and also the students!	Changing the decision making process The methods of deciding on the IT tools to be used should be democratic so that it's not a masculine & non-transparent way of decision making Free IT tools for the University community.	Checking the algorithm and the gender balance risks (they reproduce the inequality) IT experts should take into consideration the risks with personal data.
Publishing a basic guideline for each IT tool used, on how to prevent sexual harassment and GBV while using them			

GROUP 02 - HEALTH & LIFESTYLE

2.1 " Transform ideas from the health, lifestyle and way of work impacts into concrete actions to improve health permanently after the pandemic ends. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of GE. "

HEALTH & LIFESTYLE CLUSTER

Concrete actions	Target groups	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality
Clear division of roles at home	men & women, as it can reshape gender expectations	visibility of gender roles/home responsibilities within the online work space	women still carry on the heaviest load. This leads to decreased productivity and has a negative impact on mental health
Establishing "rules" for avoiding communication after certain hours of the day	Coordinators, professors, administrative staff members, students	More time for family without being bothered with work less pressure on women to overperform more time for self-care	Being seen as "lazy" or "not committed", especially if you are from other nationality Everyone assumes if you live alone you have all the time in the world to work Pressure for women to do things at home do not assume there is a family at home
Establish online and safe-distance exercising/meditation options	Family, students, teaching and non-teaching staff, everyone involved	all genders, as it plays into social roles and expectations	increased mental and physical fatigue
Healthy food initiatives (healthy food vouchers)	Everyone in the university	Less burden for women who do groceries shopping at home Allviate economic burden of purchasing healthy food	
Management establishing clear guidelines on mental health, including leaves	Measure: come from management Target: all employees	Support, especially taking into account that women suffer from depression more than men	Fear of being "the weaker one" or "not strong enough". Need of awareness, raising and support mechanisms Hierarchy in academia and business culture "only the strong survives" Even in a middle of a global pandemic, there is an expectation to be strong "Patriarchy is not threatened by the Global Pandemic" Vulnerability seen as a bad sign
Redefine these concepts: productivity does not equal efficiency.	everyone but particularly men Women understood that but are still penalized	Mental health	Increase work pressure on women Increases stress and aggression in men? (toxic masculinity)

GROUP 03 - TIME MANAGEMENT & EFFICIENCY

2.1 " Transform ideas from the clusters on time-management both at personal and professional levels into concrete actions that will improve our work-life balance permanently after the pandemic ends. Actions or measures should ideally have a positive impact on gender equality. For each proposed action, establish the target audience, the potential benefits and risks in terms of GE. "

TIME MANAGEMENT & EFFICIENCY CLUSTER

Concrete actions	Target groups	Benefits for Gender Equality	Risks for Gender Equality
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defining working hours strictly and creating a procedures for that Developing a small subtitle for everyone that says "these are the working hours, outside of those hours you are not obliged to answer". 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and teaching staff/ Administrative staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For women it would be useful due to responsibilities at home as a mother for instance Not only for mothers, but addressing issues for women tend to benefit all... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of a 'mommy track' (men continuing working long days)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trainings on time management Specialized content for working from home 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All staff (academic and professional services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All, but particularly those with any type of caring responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating added pressure (gendered) by increased expectations (even more!)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create guidelines for effective meetings (meeting preparations, outlining topics, brining time limits) Defining fixed time breaks. i.e: every 1 hour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and teaching staff All staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time saving and rebalancing of tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women even more excluded from discussions due to informal networks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create a food service to bring home after work Providing vitamin supports like vitamin c, autoimmune enhancers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All staff (academic and professional services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time saved for all who join 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who to take on this service offer? Women? Would that be a healthy option? Risky in terms of bringing virus?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment with SWW (shorter working week) e.g. four day week or 6-hour days, yet no drop in productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainability of working lives, allowing all to care more for family, community or the enviroment Not only for those with children but for all (eg less time spent in transportation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differences in productivity between women and men, carers and non carers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better teaching distribution - defragment working time defragment using red/orange/green days or weeks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teaching staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All, but particularly those with any type of caring responsibilities 	

- Slow scholarship
- Reflection on publishing practices (DORA) with a view to change 'policy'
- Research staff, particularly ECRs
- Different types/plurality of voices
- More meaningful, inclusive scholarship
- different gendered career tracks